

Customers Perception and Attitude Towards Online Banking: An Empirical Research in Context of Pakistan

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Abstract

In recent times, the global banking sector has experienced swift changes. Enhanced information technology has improved commitment tracking and fulfillment, expanded multiple online customer service channels, and expedited issue resolution. This research employs a blend of theoretical models and quantitative methods to examine the statistical links between customer perceptions and attitudes regarding online banking factors. The primary aim of this empirical study is to explore the key elements influencing customers' perceptions and attitudes towards online banking. These principal factors positively affect customer perception and attitude, with convenience being the most significant factor impacting customers' perceptions and attitudes.

Keywords: Customer perceptions, Attitude, Online banking factors.

Introduction:

Until a few years ago, banking technology was almost non-existent in Pakistan, but it has since been revolutionizing customer service and accessibility. With the advent of online banking, Internet banking, ATMs, and mobile banking, customers now enjoy greater convenience and reduced transaction costs.

Customer Perceptions in Pakistan: There are varying perceptions among customers regarding online banking in Pakistan, influenced by demographic factors and overall satisfaction with the service. The ease and convenience of online banking play significant roles in altering these perceptions. The quality of service also determines whether customers prefer internet banking. Service encounters, defined by Shostack in 1985 as “a period of time during which a consumer directly interacts with a service”, significantly impact customer satisfaction and perception of service quality.

The rapid technological advancements are major drivers of change in today's business landscape, introducing new products, services, and market opportunities. Internet banking epitomizes this shift, offering customers the realization of banking services that are accessible anytime and anywhere. However, the growth of online banking is influenced by both its convenience and security concerns. Issues like security, trust, and privacy are paramount from the consumer's perspective (Benamati and Serva 2007). Engaging with online banking requires customer involvement and familiarization with related technology (Jane et al, 2004). Regular users of e-banking need to attain a certain level of comfort with this technology for ongoing use (Servon and Kaestner 2008).

However, incidents of identity theft and hacking raise concerns among customers about conducting

financial transactions online. Despite advances in online commerce, internet banking still faces challenges in assuaging these fears. The reluctance of customers to embrace online banking, even as other online commerce barriers are overcome, is a significant issue.

Customer Attitudes: Understanding customer attitudes and activities in online banking is essential for banks to launch and sustain online services in a competitive global market. Building customer loyalty in online banking can be achieved by effectively addressing complaints and safeguarding against hacking and theft. Research shows that various factors, such as demographics, motivation, behavior towards banking technologies, and acceptance of new technology, influence consumer attitudes towards online banking. Previous experiences with computers and technology also play a role (Laforet and Li 2005). Addressing security concerns, such as spyware, viruses, and other online threats, is crucial. Chau and Lai (2003, p. 126) noted that attitudes could directly affect usage when intentions are not well-formed. Therefore, enhancing security measures in online banking could significantly boost its growth worldwide.

The objective of this study is to identify the variables that influence the customer perception and attitude and to measure whether the influence is positive or not.

The research questions related to my study are:

Question 1: Is customer perception and attitude having influence by online banking factors?

Question 2: Does risk factor have positive influence on customer perception and attitude?

Question 3: Does the convenience factor have positive influence on customer perception and attitude?

Question 4: Does the time factor have positive influence on customer perception and attitude?

Question 5: Does the privacy factor have positive influence on customer perception and attitude?

Question 6: Does the complexity factor have positive influence on customer perception and attitude?

This report serves as a valuable tool in pinpointing various challenges and advantages associated with online banking, offering significant insights for both banks and their customers. It aids banks in adopting new technologies and fostering innovation, essential for their survival in the competitive market. Additionally, this report guides banks in enhancing their online services to gain and retain customer trust.

Literature review:

In 2006, S. Arunkumar explored the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), demonstrating its effectiveness in understanding the impact of users' perceptions on their motivation to use Internet Banking. TAM, grounded in Fishbein and Ajzen's Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), posits that social behavior is driven by behavioral attitudes. This model identifies four key factors—perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and perceived enjoyment—that shape attitudes and intentions towards internet banking.

Perceived usefulness, where a user believes that their performance will improve through the use of internet banking, plays a crucial role. This belief is reinforced by actual and sustained use, especially as users gain experience across various contexts.

Davis's studies in 1989 and later in 1993, along with Taylor and Todd in 1995, underscored that perceived usefulness consistently exhibits a stronger relationship with usage than other variables,

such as attitudes, satisfaction, and perception measures. This usefulness directly impacts intentions to use, beyond its influence through attitude.

The concept of ease of use, defined by Davis in 1989 and 1993, is an individual's belief that new technology will be effortless to use. This perception is increasingly shaped by the user's direct experience with the system in various use contexts, as reiterated by S. Arunkumar in 2006. He also highlighted that perceived ease of use is a critical factor in customers' perceptions of internet banking, emphasizing minimal effort.

Customers appreciate the convenience and comfort provided by bank facilities, but security remains a major concern. The researcher emphasizes that banks can enhance consumer confidence and satisfaction by adopting a proactive, creative approach,

Dobdinga Cletus Fonchamnyo (2013) identified age, education, and marital status as significant influencers of customer attitudes towards e-banking. In terms of consumer attitudes, perceived risks play a crucial role in the adoption of online banking in China. Okey Peter Onyia et al. (2011) found that in Nigeria, gender, education level, and employment status significantly influence attitudes and intentions towards internet banking, which are also predictors of actual adoption behavior.

Theoretical framework:

Risk (independent variable)

Hypothesis 1: Customer perception and attitude towards online banking is positively correlated with risk factor:

Risk factor adopted from the article “Factors influencing online banking customer satisfaction and their importance in improving overall retention level” of shah ankit published in the journal of information and knowledge management vol.1 no.1, in 2011 and the article “Consumer attitudes system’s characteristics and internet banking adoption in Malaysia.” of Nelson Oly Ndubisi, et al published in the journal of management research news in 2006 and the other article is “ customer perception of e-banking adoption in Cameron: An empirical assessment of an extended TAM” published in the international journal of economics and finance vol.5,no.1 in 2013.

Convenience (independent variable)

Hypothesis 2: Customer perception and attitude towards online banking is positive correlated with convenience factor.

Convenience factor adopted from the study “Factors influencing online banking customer satisfaction and their importance in improving overall retention level” of shah ankit published in the journal of information and knowledge management vol.1 no.1, in 2011 and the study Consumers’ attitudes towards online and mobile banking in China of Sylvie Lafort, et al.

This factor is measured by several aspects, including the ability to access banking services anytime and anywhere, the absence of queues, time savings compared to traditional banking, and the user-friendly nature of e-banking platforms, which includes easy login procedures and the ability to regularly check transaction details and statements. Additionally, being computer literate enhances the use of e-banking services. Online banking serves as a highly profitable avenue for financial institutions, as noted by Williamson (2006). It offers customers convenience and flexibility at a lower cost compared to conventional branch banking. According to Beer (2006), the ease of online banking significantly aids people in gaining more control over their finances, leading to changes in how they withdraw cash and manage their daily financial activities.

Time (independent variable)

Hypothesis 3: Customer perception and attitude towards online banking is positive correlated with time factor.

The concept of the time factor as a significant element in internet banking is highlighted in the study "Study on Customer Perception Towards Internet Banking: Identifying Major Contributing Factors" by Divya Singhal and V. Padhmanabhan (Dec 2008). Liu and Arnett also recognized the time factor as a crucial aspect in the quality of internet banking services for customers. According to Beer (2006), saving time is a key motivator for customers opting for internet banking. Furthermore, banks can leverage their websites to provide information on products and services, offering a considerable advantage. This approach enables prospective customers to gather essential information online, ensuring that any subsequent branch visits are more focused and require less time from bank employees, as noted by Srivastava (2006).

Privacy (independent variable)

Hypothesis 4: customer perception and attitude towards online banking is positive correlated with privacy factor.

Privacy factor adopted from the study of “Factors influencing online banking customer satisfaction and their importance in improving overall retention level” of shah ankit published in the journal of information and knowledge management vol.1 no.1, in 2011.

Complexity (independent variable)

Hypothesis 5: Customer perception and attitude towards online banking is positive correlated with complexity factor.

Complexity factor adopted from the article “Consumer attitudes system’s characteristics and internet banking adoption in Malaysia.” of Nelson Oly Ndubisi, et al published in the journal of management research news in 2006.

Methodology

Research design:

The study employed a cross-sectional research approach, incorporating a correlational design to examine the connection between customer perceptions, attitudes, and online banking. It conducted a regression analysis to determine the impact of factors such as customer perception, attitudes, trust, risk, privacy, time, and complexity on the adoption of online banking. This research was both descriptive and analytical, aiming to describe and analyze the relationships among the various study variables.

The study focused on customers who have accounts with banks in Lahore and utilize online banking services. Invitations were extended to all these bank customers to participate in the research survey. Sampling involves selecting a subset of individuals from a broader statistical population to infer characteristics of the entire population. The specific sampling technique employed depends on the analysis's objectives and may include methods like simple random sampling, systematic sampling, and observational sampling. The aim is to ensure that the sample accurately represents the overall population.

On the basis of research study, sampling frame collected from the online customers and who use the online banking. Survey has been conducted through questionnaire and mail with a sample size of 200. For this study, non-probability sampling techniques are used.

A questionnaire has designed to collect the data for exploring the customer perception and attitude towards different factors of online banking in the context of Lahore and the questionnaire split into the four sections. The demographic section is also included in the start of the questionnaire which asking for the gender, age and qualification.

Data analysis:

Statistical calculations have been made, making extensive use of SPSS Software. Result of descriptive statistics has been presented in the data analysis. This study firstly analyzes the bar chart and cross tabs of the demographic variables and found the reliability and correlations of variables. The results of regression analyses are also present in data analysis section. The model of the research was proposed based on theories and observation of reality. A summary of all the hypotheses is also presented.

Reliability:

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
.703	6

Table 1

The reliability or internal consistency of a measure is gauged by its degree of consistency. Cronbach's alpha (Cronbach, 1951) is commonly employed to evaluate the reliability of a scale, with a value of 0.70 or higher considered indicative of strong reliability (O'Leary-Kelly and Vokurka, 1998). In this case, the Cronbach's alpha for the six factors is close to 0.70, indicating their reliability.

Table 2

gender					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	female	69	27.2	34.5	34.5
	male	131	51.6	65.5	100.0
	Total	200	78.7	100.0	

2 Figure

we have collected the data from the 200 sample size from the respondents who has use the online banking transactions in which 65.5% respondent's are male and 34.5% are female. In current

scenario if I compare male and female online banking users than the proportion rate of male users probably higher than the female because most of the transaction being made by male users

Table.3

age				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid less than 20 year	11	4.3	5.5	5.5
20-40	164	64.6	82.0	87.5
41-50	19	7.5	9.5	97.0
over 50	6	2.4	3.0	100.0
Total	200	78.7	100.0	

figure 3

In this study I chose the different age limits for online banking users. The age limits are less than 20 year,20-40 years,41-50 years and above 50 respectively. The table and graph shows the frequency of 20-40 age group people are high as compared to the other age group which shows the 82% people are belong to in between the age of 20 to 40 who use the online banking and 5.5% users belong to age group of less than 20 year who use the online banking.9.5% users belong to age group of 41-50 who avail online facilities and only 3% users belong to age limit of above 50 which is less as compare to the other age group.

Table 4

Qualification				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
secondary	6	2.4	3.0	3.0
diploma	15	5.9	7.5	10.5
Bachelors degree	93	36.6	46.5	57.0
Masters	72	28.3	36.0	93.0
PHD	14	5.5	7.0	100.0
Total	200	78.7	100.0	

figure 4.4

The information of qualification is categorized into five limits which is Secondary, Diploma, Bechalors, Masters and PHD respectively. The above table shows that the only 3% respondents are belong to the secondary education who use the online services and 7.5% respondents belong to the

category of diploma.46.5% people are fall in the category of bachelors, which ratio is higher as compared to the other category and 36% respondents are belong to the masters category and only 7% users are belong to the category of PHD.

Regression analysis

Table 5

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.548 ^a	.300	.282	.64314

a. Predictors: (Constant), complexity factor, time factor , convenience factor, Risk factor, privacy

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	34.445	5	6.889	16.655	.000 ^a
	Residual	80.244	194	.414		
	Total	114.689	199			

a. Predictors: (Constant), complexity factor, time factor , convenience factor, Risk factor, privacy

b. Dependent Variable: customer perception attitude of online banking

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.603	.394		1.530	.128
	Risk factor	.072	.077	.064	.944	.347
	convenience factor	.422	.073	.391	5.821	.000
	time factor	.062	.053	.078	1.160	.247
	privacy	.067	.077	.060	.875	.383
	complexity factor	.238	.096	.166	2.481	.014

a. Dependent Variable: customer perception attitude of online banking

Regression analysis is used to predict a dependent variable using one or more independent variables. A mathematical equation is developed to predict the dependent variable which is as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + b_5X_5$$

where Y indicates the dependent variable which is customer perception and attitude, X1, X2, X3, X4, X5 are the independent variables which are risk, convenience, time, privacy, complexity, and b1, b2, b3, b4, b5 are the coefficients or multipliers that describe the size of the effect the independent variables are having on the dependent variable Y, and a is the value Y is predicted to have when all the independent variables are equal to zero.

$$Y = .603 + .072X_1 + .422X_2 + .062X_3 + .067X_4 + .238X_5$$

Where:

X1= Risk factor

X2=Convenience factor

X3=Time factor

X4=Privacy factor

X5=Complexity factor

In the presented equation, the convenience factor emerges as the most influential, accounting for 42.2% of the impact on customer perception and attitude towards online banking. This is primarily because users find online banking fast and easy for conducting transactions. The complexity factor, at 23.8%, also significantly affects customer perception and attitude, though to a lesser extent than convenience but more so than other factors. The risk factor, with a 7.2% influence, impacts customer perception and attitude less than both convenience and complexity but more than time and privacy factors, which stand at 6.2% and 6.7% respectively.

The regression's R-square value is 30%, indicating that 30% of the variance in the dependent variable is predicted by the independent variables. The adjusted R-square is 28.2%, suggesting a small discrepancy of 1.80% between R² and adjusted R². This implies that if the survey were conducted across the entire population instead of a sample, the variance in outcomes would be approximately 1.80% lower. Shah Ankit's (2011) study supports this, revealing a multiple correlation coefficient (R) of 0.613 between independent and dependent variables, and an R² of 0.374, meaning about 37.4% of the outcome variability is explained by the predictors.

The F statistic of 16.655 (p-value = 0.000) confirms the significant influence of independent variables on the dependent variable at a 5% significance level, validating the model's effectiveness. Collinearity diagnostics indicate no concerns of multicollinearity, meaning that the independent variables are not overly correlated in explaining the variation in the dependent variable.

Furthermore, Dobdinga Cletus Fonchamnyo's study highlights that customer attitude towards e-banking adoption predicts 16.6% of the variance in e-banking adoption. A positive path coefficient of 0.249 suggests that a higher customer attitude towards adoption increases the likelihood of adopting e-banking.

Correlation analysis

Correlations

		customer perception attitude of online banking	Risk factor	convenience factor	time factor	privacy	complexity factor
customer perception and attitude of online banking	Pearson Correlation	1	.244**	.491**	.212**	.298**	.351**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.003	.000	.000
	N	200	200	200	200	200	200
Risk factor	Pearson Correlation	.244**	1	.212**	.382**	.329**	.286**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.003	.000	.000	.000
	N	200	200	200	200	200	200
convenience factor	Pearson Correlation	.491**	.212**	1	.117	.375**	.329**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.003		.099	.000	.000
	N	200	200	200	200	200	200
time factor	Pearson Correlation	.212**	.382**	.117	1	.305**	.273**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	.000	.099		.000	.000
	N	200	200	200	200	200	200
privacy	Pearson Correlation	.298**	.329**	.375**	.305**	1	.279**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	200	200	200	200	200	200
complexity factor	Pearson Correlation	.351**	.286**	.329**	.273**	.279**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	200	200	200	200	200	200

The correlation coefficient can range from -1 to +1.

This study's results regarding the correlation coefficients indicate that the dependent variables (customer perception and attitude) are highly correlated with the independent variables. The hypotheses and their corresponding results are as follows:

Risk Factor

Hypothesis (H1): Customer perception and attitude towards online banking are positively correlated with the risk factor. Result: The correlation coefficient for the risk factor is 0.244, showing positive results at a significance level of 5%, indicating a significant influence on customer perception and attitude. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis.

Convenience Factor

H2: Customer perception and attitude towards online banking are positively correlated with the convenience factor. Result: The correlation coefficient for the convenience factor is 49.1%, indicating a strong relationship with customer perception and attitude.

Time Factor

H3: Customer perception and attitude towards online banking are positively correlated with the time factor. Result: The correlation coefficient for the time factor is 21.2%, suggesting a positive influence on customer perception and attitude.

Privacy Factor

H4: Customer perception and attitude towards online banking are positively correlated with the privacy factor. Result: The correlation percentage for the privacy factor is 29.8%, indicating a direct correlation with customer perception and attitude.

Complexity Factor

H5: Customer perception and attitude towards online banking are positively correlated with the complexity factor. Result: The correlation percentage for the complexity factor is 35.1%, also showing a positive relationship.

Discussion and findings

The ratio of male who using online banking is 65.5% which is more than the females. Online banking mostly uses the respondents in the age limit of 20-40 and they are satisfied with the online banking transactions moreover above 40 ratio is comparatively low as compared to other age limits. Online banking transactions also use by those who are familiar with the system and it is mostly based on educational level and knowledge.

The R-square of the model is 30% which shows the variation in dependent variable that is predicted by independent variables. This implies that factors such as risk, convenience, time, privacy, and complexity significantly impact customer perception and attitudes towards online banking. Additionally, Dobdinga Cletus Fonchamnyo's research highlights that the overall adoption of e-banking is closely linked to customer attitudes, accounting for 16.6% of the variation in e-banking adoption rates. The study revealed a positive correlation, with a coefficient of 0.249, suggesting that a more favorable customer attitude towards e-banking increases the likelihood of its adoption.

In the correlation analysis all the variable is significant at the level of 0.05% and we reject the entire null hypothesis because there is positive and direct relationship exists between dependant and independent variables. The correlation between customer perception and attitude, and convenience factor is approximately 50% its means the customer is more care about convenience during performing online transactions and according to this ratio respondents find online banking fast to use, easy to manage their finances and easier way to solve the banking needs

After convenience factor the ratio of complexity factor is 35% which shows it also influence the customer perception and attitude as the some respondents said it is an easy way to conduct banking transactions and they find easy to remember the password of ATM card. The Nelson Oly Ndubisi,et

al in his study also find that internet banking is less complex that does not require a lot of mental and physical efforts to accomplish banking task. The result also shows that privacy factor is also more concern for the online users as the above correlation table the correlation is 29.8% which shows also the positive and strong relationship with the customer perceptions and attitude and the respondents said they confident over the privacy aspects of online banking and bank does not provide their personal information to the others without their consent. Moreover the risk factor correlation percentage is 24.4% which shows the users positive attitude towards the risk as they said online banking transactions is not risky anymore and they trust the banking technologies the banks implemented in order to keep online banking secure and there is less chances of risk of error. The correlation of time factor is 21.2% which also shows positive relationship but this ratio is less than the all other factors but the respondents reveal that there is not much time required to performed online banking transactions and not so many time is required to learn to use online banking. The customer perception and attitude is not totally based on these factors its means there is some other factors as well prevail.

Recommendations:

Ensuring the secure delivery of confidential information from banks to customers and building trust in the bank's privacy measures are crucial for fostering effective relationships and enhancing long-term customer satisfaction. Research suggests that banks should enhance their online banking technology to attract more users and reduce service fees, making transactions more accessible. Additionally, simplifying the online banking system can positively influence customer perceptions and attitudes, encouraging acceptance of new technology and maximizing the benefits of online banking services.

Conclusion:

The results empirically substantiate that using of online banking services play a vital role in the customer perception and attitude. From the above results I conclude that customer perceptions and attitude is greatly affected by risk factor, convenience factor, time factor, privacy factor, and complexity factor. The percentage of independent variables is not so high its means the customer perception and attitude is not totally based on these factors so there is some other factors as well prevail in online banking that also influence the customer perception and attitude and because of limited time I did not consider these factors.

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